

WHERE:

280 Genesis HealthCare nursing homes in 21 states

WHEN?

February 15 to March 31, 2021

WHO?

18,242 vaccinated nursing home residents; 3990 unvaccinated nursing home residents

THE POPULATION

• Genesis HealthCare nursing home residents

• **18,242 residents had received at least one dose of the mRNA COVID-19 vaccine by February 15, 2021;** 13,048 of those had received a second dose of mRNA vaccine by February 15, 2021; 3990 were unvaccinated throughout the course of the study

Vaccinated residents identified as:
78.7% White, **12.4%** Black, **4.2%** Hispanic/Latino, **2.3%** Other, and **2.4%** Unknown

Unvaccinated residents identified as:
67.6% White, **20.2%** Black, **4.5%** Hispanic/Latino, **2.3%** Other, and **5.4%** Unknown

• **More than 75% had at least one risk factor for COVID-19** such as hypertension, diabetes, or heart disease

MEASURES & OBSERVATIONS

1. Residents were tested for COVID-19 if they were exposed to or showed any symptoms of COVID-19.

2. **Surveillance testing was conducted every 3 to 7 days** in facilities with any positive cases in the prior two weeks.

3. Researchers compared participant vaccination status to the rate of positive COVID-19 tests at different time points.

KEY FINDINGS

1. The rate of COVID-19 infection decreased over time among both vaccinated and unvaccinated residents.
2. Most residents who tested positive for COVID-19 had no symptoms.
3. Nursing homes in counties with a high number of COVID-19 infections had a greater number of infections.
4. **COVID-19 cases among residents who received 2 doses decreased sooner** than cases among residents who received at least one dose or were unvaccinated.

CONCLUSIONS

1. **COVID-19 vaccines are protective against infection** for both vaccinated and unvaccinated nursing home residents.
2. Vaccinating a large number of nursing home residents may protect a small number of unvaccinated residents.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Vaccination, masking, and surveillance testing are recommended for nursing home residents to slow the spread of COVID-19.

Citation: White EM, Yang X, Blackman C, Feifer RA, Gravenstein S, Mor V. Incident SARS-CoV-2 infection among mRNA-vaccinated and unvaccinated nursing home residents. *New Engl. J. Med.* 2021;385(5):474-476. doi: 10.1056/NEJMc2104849

This summary was completed in March 2022. This summary includes only results from one single study. Other studies may find different results.

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To read the published research article, visit radx-up.org.

A Research Collaboration with

The IMPACT-C: Improving Vaccine Uptake in Skilled Nursing Facilities project is a collaborative dedicated to developing and evaluating SARS-CoV-2 testing strategies in highly vulnerable skilled nursing facilities, residents and workers.